
FIVE HOSPITAL WORLDS: WEBOTS SOURCE FILES

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Open-Source Robotic Worlds for 3D Proficiency Prior to Sim-to-Sim RL Workflows

Problem & Solution

- 1) **Problem:** Building different enhanced three-dimensional medical environments can take significant time, effort
- 2) **Solution:** LLM Opus 4.5 Extended developed different inpatient worlds, fixed errors, and optimized performance
- 3) **Progression:** Basic through advanced use of robots was determined by comparing to README.md instructions

Five Webots Worlds

- 1) **Hospital Hallway Robot**, Basic: User manipulation of robot, and robot proceeds to “door1”
 - a) 27 KB, World: hospital_hallway.wbt. Controller: hallway_robot.py
 - b) 24 MB, Demonstration Video: Hospital Hallway Robot.mp4
- 2) **Hospital Supply Delivery**, Basic: Robot approaches “bed_101” on opposite site of room
 - a) 23 KB, World: hospital_floor.wbt. Controller: delivery_robot.py
 - b) 48 MB, Demonstration Video: Hospital Supply Delivery.mp4
- 3) **Hospital Corridor Robot**, Basic: Robot first aligned by user to make contact with “supply_cart”
 - a) 29 KB, World: hospital_corridor.wbt. Controller: transport_controller.py
 - b) 17 MB, Demonstration Video: Hospital Corridor Robot.mp4
- 4) **Emergency Room Multi Robot**, Intermediate: Three robots - Two reach “nurse_station” and “reception”
 - a) 40 KB, World: emergency_room.wbt. Controller: er_coordinator.py, er_robot.py
 - b) 09 MB, Demonstration Video: Emergency Room Multi Robot.mp4
- 5) **Exam Room Sensor Robot**, Advanced: Sensor robot avoids two walls based on two different approaches
 - a) 55 KB, World: exam_room.wbt. Controller: sensor_robot.py
 - b) 76 MB, Demonstration Video: Exam Room Sensor Robot.mp4

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Figure 1: Hospital World Shown = 4) Emergency Room Multi Robot